

Plastics Fate and Effects in the Human Body

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Executive Summary

This report provides an overview of the progress made in Task 6.2 of the PlasticsFatE project, which focuses on delivering training in analytical and detection methods related to micro and nanoplastics (MNPs).

The training sessions encompassed both physical events, such as workshops, and virtual sessions, including webinars, aimed at disseminating knowledge within the consortium and to the wider research community.

Key achievements include the successful delivery of physical and virtual training sessions, with topics ranging from hazard assessment to risk management and standardization processes.

Notable events include the "Advances in hazard assessment of micro- and nanoplastics and contaminants in humans" workshop and the "Introduction to and Training on Risk Assessment for Micro and Nanoplastics" webinar.

Overall, partners have diligently adhered to the work plan, and their contributions have significantly enhanced the project's performance and outreach.

1. Description of task

Task 6.2 describes how PlasticsFatE has availed itself of the knowledge and expertise of different partners in the technical work packages to deliver training in analytical and detection methods informed by project results. Task 6.2 produced D6.4, delivering “two physical and two virtual training events to impart knowledge gained within PlasticsFatE to the wider research community. Material will also be downloadable from the website and information provided that is accessible to a wider audience.”

Accordingly, four events were organised, two physical and two virtual, to convey knowledge on the application of a select range of preparatory methods and tools for the analysis of micro and nanoplastics (MNPs). The training sessions were designed to be fully accessible to early career researchers (ECRs) within the PlasticsFatE consortium, who were encouraged to participate. In addition, where possible, we invited participation from our sister CUSP projects and complementary initiatives working to increase our understanding of the fate of plastics and their impact on human health.

Where content was not confidential, training materials have been, or will be, made easily accessible to a wider audience via the CUSP Zenodo community and the PlasticsFatE website.

PlasticsFatE partners have also delivered additional in-person training/instruction sessions when opportunities have arisen.

2. Description of work & main achievements

2.1 Physical Training Session 1:

Title: Advances in hazard assessment of micro- and nanoplastics and contaminants in humans.

Location: STAMI, Oslo

Date: 22nd – 23rd June 2023

This first physical training workshop was aimed at supporting ECRs and was delivered by STAMI in collaboration with other PlasticsFatE partners. The content (Figure 1) focused on advances in hazard assessment of MNPs and additives/adsorbed contaminants (A/C) in humans. The workshop took place after the PlasticsFatE General Assembly held at STAMI, enabling participants and lecturers to take part more easily.

The overall objective was to update ECRs on recent methodological developments for quantifying hazard effects of micro- and nanoplastics in humans. The workshop included a series of lectures that provided the necessary information/concepts and overview of methods in plastic particle toxicology, as well as a hands-on demonstration of the Cloud exposure systems from Vitrocell (Germany).

Programme and Speakers

DAY 1 (22.06.2023)			DAY 2 (23.06.2023)		
8:45-09:00	Introduction		9:00-09:45	Lecture 4 MNP & A/C: Dosimetry advances and challenges	Dr. Francesco Barbera (UNITO, Italia)
9:00-09:45	Keynote lecture Overview of the latest achievements in plastic particle toxicology	Prof. Phil Demokritou (Harvard University, USA)	09:45-10:30	Lecture 5 MNP & A/C: Challenges of detection and quantification in vitro and in vivo	Dr. Anja Ramsberger (UBT, Germany)
09:45-10:30	Lecture 1 MNP & A/C in the airways: methodological advances on the assessment of hazards associated with the respiratory tract	Dr. Sonja Boland (Université de Paris, France)	10:30- 11:00	Coffee break	
10:30- 11:00	Coffee break		11:00-11:45	Lecture 6 MNP & A/C: In vitro - In vivo correlations	Prof. Tobias Stoeger (HZM, Germany)
11:00-11:45	Lecture 2 MNP & A/C in the GIT: methodological advances on the assessment of hazards associated with the gastro-intestinal tract	Dr. Alba Tamargo (CSIC, Spain)	11:45- 12:15	Summary and take-home message	
11:45-12:30	Lecture 3 MNP & A/C in the immune system: methodological advances on the assessment of hazards associated with the immune system	Dr. Alberto Katsumiti (GAIKER, Spain)			
12:30 – 14:00	Lunch				
14:00 - 16:00	Hands-ON with Vitrocell ALI system/lab visit	Dr. Paul Schumacher (VITROCELL, Germany)			

Figure 1: STAMI Training Workshop Programme

Participants

Nine ECRs from PlasticsFatE attended the lectures, which were delivered by eight lecturers from various PlasticsFatE research institutions who joined forces under the coordination of STAMI and OPTIMAT.

Content and Proceedings

Prof Philip Demokritou (Harvard University), a PlasticsFatE expert advisory board member, opened the workshop with a keynote lecture on the potential health issues associated with exposure to MNPs, particularly to acute altered lipid metabolism upon ingestion of MNPs. Adapted methods and approaches for in vitro characterization of toxic effects in airways, gastro-intestinal tract and the immune system were respectively described by Dr Sonja Boland (University of Paris), Dr Alba Tamargo (CSIC) and Dr Alberto Katsumiti (GAIKER).

The physico-chemical properties of MNPs in various media and the associated kinetics were introduced by Dr Francesco Barbero (UNITO). He emphasized the necessity to have good characterization of particle dosimetry in every exposure system in order to achieve relevant and reproducible data.

Another important issue was the detection of MNPs in complex matrices. This was presented by Dr Anja Ramsperger (UBT, Germany) who described the possibilities and limitations of different detection methods. Dr Tobias Stöger (HZM, Germany), a PlasticsFatE expert advisory board member, ended the workshop with a lecture on the correlation between in vitro and in vivo studies of hazard effects.

As the training content included unpublished material, it was uploaded to the project's shared filespace on MS Teams. As results are published, some of the material may be made publicly

available. At present, the content delivered by Dr. Sonja Boland (UP) is now available here: <https://zenodo.org/records/10959587>

Impact

As an example of impact, the presentation delivered by Dr. Sonja Boland provided ECRs with a comprehensive overview of the latest methodological advances in the assessment of MNPs hazards in the respiratory tract. The session's impact was particularly significant in equipping ECRs with practical knowledge and tools that they could directly apply in their own research settings. Through detailed insights into particle deposition mechanisms in the respiratory system, challenges in dosimetry, and advanced in vitro models such as air-liquid interface cultures, organoids, and co-culture systems, participants gained a nuanced understanding of how to more accurately simulate and assess human exposure scenarios.

The session also highlighted the importance of characterising the physico-chemical properties of MNPs and navigating experimental interferences—fundamental for designing robust and reproducible studies. Importantly, the exposure systems and in vitro dosimetry tools introduced (e.g. Vitrocell®, ISDD model, and imaging flow cytometry) enabled ECRs to critically evaluate and refine their experimental designs to better reflect real-world exposure conditions.

In sum, the training event not only deepened conceptual knowledge but also empowered ECRs to return to their laboratories with enhanced capabilities to conduct relevant, cutting-edge research in, for example, inhalation toxicology, ultimately supporting the wider goals of the PlasticsFatE project.

Figure 2: Participants at the Training Event, STAMI, Oslo.

Standing from left: Sara Michelini (UL), Giulia Antonello (UNITO), Lara Faccani (CNR), Anja Ramsperger (UBT), Sebastian Purker (BOKU), Maria Kazour (ULeiden), Safaa Mawas (UParis), Øyvind Haugen (STAMI), Paul Schumacher (Vitrocell) and sitting from left: Francesco Barbero (UNITO), Alberto Katsumiti (Gaiker), Katharina Juengert (FAU) and Andreas Solberg Sagen (STAMI).

Photo: Anani Afanou (STAMI)

2.2 Physical Training Session 2:

Title: CUSP meets the Collaborative Research Centre on Microplastics. MP – Environmental and Human Health: Are there Common Solutions?

Location: University of Bayreuth, Germany

Date: 11th – 13th November 2024

The second training event was organised by the University of Bayreuth in collaboration with the Collaborative Research Centre at UBT. This three-day event offered a unique blend of theoretical exploration and hands-on training featuring an integrated programme of expert-led workshops, scientific presentations, and an immersive laboratory training experience.

Programme and Speakers

While the theoretical components—described in detail in D6.5 ‘Regular events to present and discuss project output and help shape future activities with external stakeholders’—offered insights into standardisation, regulatory frameworks, and ongoing research across CUSP projects, it was the final day’s hands-on training that gave the participants direct exposure to the advanced tools and techniques employed in MNP research.

The content of this practical element (Figure 3) was delivered by four experts in the field:

- Dr Daniel Wagner – Production and characterization of microplastic particles
- Dr Martin Löder – Key Lab Microplastic analytics: Identification of microplastic in complex matrices
- Prof Dr Jürgen Senker – NMR Spectroscopy for the characterization of microplastics
- Prof Dr Holger Kress – Optical tweezers to investigate microplastic particle-cell interactions.

Programme
Wednesday 13th November

10:00	Welcome & Group Formation	<i>Dr Anja Ramsperger</i>
10:30	Parallel Lab Tours	<i>PhD Guides</i>
12:00	Close	<i>Prof Dr Christian Laforsch, University of Bayreuth</i>
	Lunch	

Dr Daniel Wagner	Dr Martin Löder	Prof Dr Jürgen Senker	Prof Dr Holger Kress
Production and characterization of microplastic particles	Key Lab Microplastic analytics Identification of microplastic in complex matrices	NMR spectroscopy for the characterization of microplastics	Optical tweezers to investigate microplastic particle-cell interactions

UNIVERSITÄT BAYREUTH

PlasticsFatE

SFB MIKROPLASTIK

Figure 3: Practical training programme

Participants

The target participants were the ECRs from PlasticsFatE and its sister CUSP projects, and the Collaborative Research Centre at UBT. In sum 50 participants (24 female and 26 male) attended the whole three- day workshop and training event at UBT.

Figure 4: Participants at the UBT Workshop and Training Event

Content and Proceedings

The theoretical content and proceedings are described in D6.5, hence this section will focus on the content and proceedings of the practical element of the training, which took place on the final day of the workshop.

For logistical purposes, the participants were divided into four groups that then rotated through four laboratory stations:

- **Production and Characterization of Microplastic Particles**
Led by Dr. Daniel Wagner, this session introduced participants to methods for producing and characterising microplastic (MP) test materials. ECRs learned how cryomilling and electrospinning techniques are applied to create controlled MP and MNP samples. This foundational knowledge is crucial for ensuring standardised, reproducible test materials in research and regulatory settings.
- **Key Lab Microplastic analytics: Identification of microplastic in complex matrices**
Dr. Martin Löder, Head of UBT's Key Lab for Microplastic Analytics, guided participants through the full process of microplastic sampling, purification, and analysis. Through a tour of the highly specialized lab facilities, attendees gained a deeper appreciation for quality assurance/quality control (QA/QC) protocols essential to producing valid data for regulatory purposes. This was particularly relevant to the workshop's emphasis on harmonization and standardization of MNP analytics.
- **NMR Spectroscopy for the characterization of microplastics**
Prof. Dr. Jürgen Senker introduced participants to the capabilities of the North Bavarian NMR Centre. By explaining how nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy can be employed to characterize the chemical structure and properties of microplastic particles, ECRs saw first-

hand how advanced instrumentation contributes to differentiating polymer types and assessing degradation.

- Optical tweezers to investigate microplastic particle-cell interactions.

In a session led by Prof. Dr. Holger Kress, participants learned how biophysical techniques can be applied to MNP toxicology. Using holographic optical and magnetic tweezers, the session demonstrated how researchers can manipulate individual microplastic particles to investigate their interactions with living cells—an essential technique in understanding potential health risks

Impact

In sum, the practical sessions not only allowed ECRs to observe state-of-the-art equipment but also encouraged dialogue with lab leaders, offering insights into the design and execution of complex experiments. The participants gained a clear overview of the state-of-the-art methods for producing well-characterized microplastic particles and the analytical techniques for purifying and identifying these particles in complex matrices. Furthermore, they were also introduced to unique approaches, such as NMR for characterizing microplastics and investigating particle-cell interactions using optical tweezers. Many participants cited this hands-on exposure as highly useful for their own research.

Complementing these practical elements, the earlier workshop sessions provided context and theoretical perspectives that are often overlooked. Keynotes from Prof. Dr. Christian Laforsch and Dr. Giorgia Carratta examined the evolving landscape of microplastic regulation from both scientific and legal perspectives. ECRs participated in lightning talks, poster sessions, and collaborative discussions, all designed to build communication skills and stimulate cross-disciplinary collaboration.

The emphasis on standardization and regulation across sessions reinforced the importance of aligning scientific methods with real-world regulatory needs. The event highlighted that innovation in microplastic research must be accompanied by clarity in analytical methods and consistency in data quality to support evidence-based policymaking.

The combination of theory and practice created a balanced approach for fostering professional growth. With 50 attendees (24 female and 26 male) from across Europe, the event created a dynamic learning environment for ECRs, enabling them to informally engage with more senior experts through social activities—including a welcome dinner and a visit to Bayreuth's Winterdorf—which further strengthened these professional ties.

Participants left the workshop with:

- **Hands-on experience** in producing and analysing microplastics using advanced laboratory techniques.
- **Improved understanding** of how experimental methods translate into regulatory contexts.
- **Clarity on challenges and gaps** in MNP analytics and policy development.
- **Opportunities for future collaboration** across PlasticsFatE, CUSP, and UBT's research infrastructure.

- **Resources to disseminate their work**, including poster uploads to Zenodo, the PlasticsFatE website and the CUSP newsletter.

The event's strength lay in its ability to blend scientific exchange with practical learning—equipping ECRs with knowledge and skills that they can apply in real-world regulatory, academic, and industrial settings.

2.3 Virtual Training Session 1:

Title: Introduction to and Training on Risk Assessment for Micro and Nano Plastics

Location: Online

Date: 29th March 2022

In 2022, PlasticsFatE partners (UFZ, BOKU, ITENE, UP, DECHEMA, OPTIMAT), organised and took part in a series of online workshops in collaboration with the CUSP projects. The first – the forerunner to a series of three - was delivered solely by PlasticsFatE partners, with the remaining three delivered as a joint activity with the CUSP WG5 (Risk assessment), and as part of Task 4.5. PlasticsFatE's role in the series of three workshops is described in more detail in section 2.5 of this deliverable.

This first training workshop was held on 29th March 2022 and titled “Introduction to and Training on Risk Assessment for Micro and Nano Plastics” (<https://zenodo.org/records/6421451>).

This interactive event provided an introduction to risk assessment for micro and nanoplastics and invited participants to fully engage in the live session.

Programme and Speakers

Lecture title	Lecturer
Welcome and Introduction	Rudolf Reuther, ENAS
Risk Assessment & Management - Setting the scene Introduction to current regulation Methods and tools for improved risk assessment of MNP etc	Dana Kühnel, UFZ
Discussion / Feedback round Crucial topics and issues to consider for human risk assessment (mentimeter query) Afterwards discussion with the participants	Dana Kühnel, UFZ
BREAK	
PlasticsFatE - First approach for the Decision Support System The ITENE DSS approach	Blanca Pozuelo Rollón, ITENE
Feedback Session Feedback on the approach and on the tools used Which tools are being developed, other tools and how are they provided? Discussion on data sharing in the project, implementation in the web based DSS platform	Blanca Pozuelo Rollón, ITENE
BREAK	
Prospective multi-criteria decision support system for plastics (PMCDs) Introduction on multi-criteria decision analysis, concept of the PMCDs, intended use in the context of PlasticsFatE	Bernd Giese, Boku
Discussion / Feedback round - main criteria ranked by the audience via mentimeter	Sebastian Purker, Boku
BREAK	
Results of mentimeter query Feedback from the participants on a) the relevance of the proposed criteria and b) what could be important features of the tool e.g. considering the generation of micro/nano plastics from a product, most relevant exposure pathways etc. Open discussion on a) the information needs for the different criteria and b) for the application of the tool Discussion on other PMCDs data needs and on the data each partner can provide	Bernd Giese, Sebastian Purker, Boku
Importance of data management Recommendations/suggestions for data management by the RD manager in PlasticsFatE	Damjana Drobne, Univ. Ljubljana, presented by Dana Kühnel, UFZ
Closing remarks	Dana Kühnel, UFZ

Figure 5 Programme and Speakers for the Risk Assessment workshop

Participants

The training event attracted a diverse and multidisciplinary group of participants from across Europe, including PhD students, postdocs, academic researchers, regulators, industry professionals, and environmental consultants. Many of the ECRs were engaged in applied toxicology, exposure science, environmental chemistry, or regulatory affairs, and brought with them a practical need to understand risk assessment processes and data requirements.

The broader professional community included individuals working on material development, policy implementation, and safety assessment for consumer products and industrial processes. Participants indicated plans to use the learning in a variety of ways: aligning their lab methods with regulatory expectations, informing the design of safer polymeric materials, contributing to ISO working groups or CEN committees, and enhancing transparency in science-policy interfaces.

Content and Proceedings

Lecturers delivered an introduction to risk assessment for MNPs and participants were given an overview on the basics of risk assessment and various tools to support the assessment procedure. The lecturers then received feedback from the participants on data needs and

availability as well as which tools might exist in the portfolios of the MNP projects and/or CUSP Cluster partners.

Following a welcome by PlasticsFatE's Scientific Coordinator, Rudolf Reuther (ENAS), the workshop began with an overview by Dana Kühnel (UFZ) on the current regulation of polymers. Some of the main tools and methods for risk assessment were shown. In a feedback round supported by a mentimeter survey, crucial topics and issues to consider for human risk assessment were discussed.

In a second lecture, Blanca Pozuelo Rollón (ITENE) demonstrated a first approach for the decision support system (DSS) that she and her colleagues are developing. The feedback session enabled a discussion of impressions of the approach and the tools used. The focus was placed on existing tools, tools under development, and additional tools, before an overview of how they are provided and integrated into risk assessment. A discussion on data sharing in the project and the implementation in the web-based DSS platform completed this session.

Bernd Giese (BOKU) then introduced the Prospective Multi-Criteria Decision Support System for plastics (PMCDS) and its intended use in the context of PlasticsFatE. In a subsequent discussion round, Sebastian Purker (BOKU) offered the audience the opportunity to add and rank the main criteria via mentimeter; for example, on the relevance of the proposed criteria and what could be important features of the tool. In an open discussion session, the results of the feedback from the mentimeter survey were collected and discussed.

A final discussion on the information needs for the different criteria and for the application of the tool gave indications of other PMCDS data needs, on the data partners are collecting, and how they can be integrated into the PMCDS.

Finally, on behalf of Damjana Drobne (UL) Dana Kühnel delivered a lecture on the importance of data management as well as the recommendations and suggestions of the Research Data Manager in PlasticsFatE.

The event concluded with a summary of the topics addressed, delivered by Dana Kühnel (Figure 6).

The image shows a virtual training workshop interface. It features two presentation slides, one on top of the other, with a sidebar on the right showing participant avatars. The top slide is titled 'Wrap-up' and 'Part I', listing four bullet points. The bottom slide is titled 'Wrap-up' and 'Part III', listing five bullet points. The sidebar on the right shows a vertical stack of avatars, with one active participant visible in a larger window. The date and time '2022-03-29 13:09:43' are visible at the bottom right of the top slide, and '2022-03-29 13:14:15' at the bottom right of the bottom slide.

Slide 21:

Wrap-up

Part I

- Uncertainties, knowledge gaps on MNP: differences in exposure, fate and hazard potential; crucial characteristics defining exposure, fate, hazard
- Realistic materials for testing, reference material
- Characterisation & analytical methods development
- Harmonisation of vocabulary, nomenclature, definition, but also methods....

Part II

- Purpose and content of decision support system (DSS)
- Use of case studies, examples, use cases
- Feedback of end users on structure of DSS
- Interaction with CUSP on data management,
- eNanoMapper

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2022-03-29 13:09:43

Slide 22:

Wrap-up

Part III

- Early indicators: valuable input
- Importance of additives, chemicals, fillers
- Imbalance in hazard and exposure data availability
- Need for grouping and read-across approaches
- Elmer Swart: With colleagues from RIVM, BAuA, Bfr and UBA, we have developed an approach to early risk assessment of advanced materials, a first version of this approach was recently published on the RIVM website, with much overlap in the criteria you have already identified. See <https://www.rivm.nl/documenten/ewarn-brochure-o>

22

2022-03-29 13:14:15

Figure 6: Summary of the first Virtual Training Workshop

All materials and videos of the workshop have been made available here: <https://zenodo.org/records/6421451>.

Impact

The event made a significant impact by advancing participants' understanding of integrated risk assessment for MNPs, particularly with regard to regulatory preparedness and safe-by-design innovation. The session brought together diverse tools and conceptual frameworks, including the DSS and PMCDS, with a strong focus on early-stage risk governance.

These tools were developed to support informed decision-making by assessing exposure, hazard potential, and life-cycle factors of MNPs. Attendees gained insight into how these systems can help identify critical data needs, evaluate the risk potential of different plastic materials, and guide design strategies to reduce the emergence of MNPs.

By providing hands-on demonstrations of how to apply criteria weighting, score alternatives, and derive ranked options, the training enabled participants to translate complex theoretical frameworks into practical evaluation tools tailored to their own research contexts.

In particular, early career researchers and other participants could take these learnings back to their labs and apply them in scenario modelling, material assessment, and experimental design, particularly for developing and testing safer alternatives. Moreover, the practical framing of the workshop helped demystify the complexity of regulatory frameworks and highlighted how academic researchers can contribute effectively to ongoing risk governance processes.

The mentimeter survey conducted during the session played a crucial role in collecting user feedback that could shape subsequent and future iterations of the DSS and PMCDS tools. Responses revealed a clear interest in improved usability, greater clarity on structure, and the integration of case studies and regulatory guidance relevant to specific user groups. Many respondents also emphasised the importance of tailoring the platform to non-experts, such as industry innovators or policy advisors, who may lack in-depth toxicological expertise. These insights provided concrete direction for the development team, especially regarding platform navigation, tool integration, and the inclusion of decision trees or use-case walk-throughs.

Suggestions for additional features—such as guidance for harmonised testing methods or data input templates—are likely to feed into refinement cycles for both tools. Importantly, feedback also underscored the value of connecting with other Work Packages and ensuring that experimental results and data management protocols feed directly into the DSS backend.

Participants indicated plans to use the learning in a variety of ways: aligning their lab methods with regulatory expectations, informing the design of safer polymeric materials, contributing to ISO working groups or CEN committees, and enhancing transparency in science-policy interfaces. The workshop thus served as a valuable knowledge transfer opportunity, enabling both academic and applied actors to integrate cutting-edge risk governance tools into their own domains. The variety of perspectives represented in the event also encouraged interdisciplinary exchange and highlighted the importance of co-developing tools that are adaptable to multiple contexts within the MNP research and policy landscape.

2.4 Virtual Training Session 2:

Title: The Why and How of Standardization

Location: Online

Date: 4th July 2024

This second virtual training event, organised by UBA, was designed to introduce and engage ECRs and other interested stakeholders with the principles and practicalities of standardization in the field of microplastics. The session was framed as a response to the growing need for harmonized approaches in microplastic research, monitoring and regulation.

The event offered a structured and accessible entry point for participants with little or no previous experience in standardization processes. It also created a platform for broader engagement with stakeholders from regulatory bodies, industry, research institutions and national standardization committees.

Programme and Speakers

Time	Session Title	Speaker
13:00–13:15	Welcome and Opening Remarks	Rudolf Reuther (ENAS); Lesley Tobin (OPTIMAT)
13:15–13:40	Standardization process and overview of microplastic standardization	Dr. Ulrike Braun (UBA)
13:40–14:05	ISO/TC 16094-2 – Status update on vibrational spectroscopy methods for water analysis	Nizar Benismail (Nestlé Waters QA)
14:05–14:15	Break	
14:15–14:50	What we need for the future: Ecotoxicology of Microplastics in Standardization	Marcus Lukas (UBA)
14:50–15:00	Closing	Lesley Tobin (OPTIMAT); Dr. Ulrike Braun (UBA)

Figure 7: Agenda for Virtual Training Event on Standardization

Content and Proceedings

Dr. Ulrike Braun (UBA), convener of ISO/TC 61/SC 14-WG4 “Microplastics”, opened the technical sessions by explaining the foundational role of standardization in environmental regulation. She talked participants through the highly formalised stages of international standard development, such as the Preliminary Work Item (PWI), New Work Item Proposal (NWIP), Committee Draft (CD), and Final Draft International Standard (FDIS), culminating in ISO publication. Participants were also introduced to key coordinating structures like ISO, CEN and national committees operating under agreements such as the Vienna Agreement.¹

The session demonstrated how standardization differs from academic research, requiring broad stakeholder involvement, data harmonization, and consensus-building between actors from academia, industry, and policy. Through this framing, participants were shown how their research can actively contribute to shaping regulatory frameworks—an essential step for moving towards more effective microplastic management at a European and global level.

¹ Agreement on technical cooperation between ISO and CEN (1991), aiming to prevent duplication and promote efficient standardization efforts. <https://www.cencenelec.eu/about-cen/cen-and-iso-cooperation/>

Nizar Benismail provided an overview of the current status of ISO 16094-2, focusing on vibrational spectroscopy methods for detecting microplastics in low-turbidity waters, such as drinking water. He discussed the rationale behind method selection, interlaboratory validations, and the critical importance of detection sensitivity and standardization across laboratories.

Marcus Lukas highlighted the urgent need to standardize ecotoxicological assessment methods for microplastics. His session identified methodological gaps and the challenges of extrapolating laboratory findings to real-world impacts. Participants were encouraged to get involved in developing new standards in this emerging area—an important opportunity to integrate research findings into formal regulatory processes.

Participants

The training drew a diverse audience of researchers and professionals from across Europe. A large proportion of the participants identified as ECRs, doctoral students, and scientists working directly with microplastics. Motivations for attending the training were varied and reflected the growing need to understand and engage with standardization processes.

Participants were asked to provide their reasons for wanting to participate in the training event. Responses included the following:

- *“I am working on the fate study of microplastics in aquatic environments and want to understand how international standards can guide or be influenced by such research.”*
- *“I am a PhD student working on biodegradable microplastics and I’m interested in contributing to the development of international standards.”* (Participant, Aarhus University)
- *“I have been involved in collaborative projects related to microplastic research and would like to better understand the role of harmonised methods in ensuring data comparability.”* (Participant, University of Vigo)
- *“As an ECR, I want to get an overview of the complex and seemingly opaque world of standardization and see how I can contribute.”* (Participant, University Medical Center Utrecht)
- *“Our work in an applied context relies on data that will stand up in regulatory discussions. Understanding standardization helps ensure we’re generating actionable science.”* (Participant, Polymateria)

Participants expressed an interest in learning how to apply the training content in the following ways:

- Aligning their laboratory protocols with emerging standardization methods (e.g., spectroscopy and sample preparation techniques).
- Identifying opportunities to contribute to working groups within ISO, CEN or national bodies.
- Ensuring that their data generation processes are robust and transferable across labs, especially in interlaboratory comparisons.
- Designing studies that could contribute to the currently underdeveloped field of microplastic ecotoxicology.

Impact

The workshop succeeded in increasing participants' understanding of how standardization underpins regulatory processes at national and EU levels. It also served to 'demystify' the standard development process and show how academic and industry researchers can contribute in practical ways. Moreover, the training generated interest among the attendees to contribute to future standardization efforts, especially in the field of ecotoxicology as well as encouraging interdisciplinary collaboration between environmental scientists, toxicologists, and standards developers.

Finally, by highlighting existing and draft standards relevant to the PlasticsFatE project, particularly ISO 16094 series on microplastics in water, the participants were able to add to their body of knowledge regarding the standards themselves. Feedback from participants highlighted that the session had "opened new perspectives on how research can support policy," and that they felt "better equipped to navigate and contribute to standardization committees and discussions."

2.5 Additional Training Delivered

2.5.1 Workshop 3 of 3 Human Risk assessment of Micro- and Nanoplastics (MNPs)

Title: Practice-based analysis of data needs, availability, reuse and gaps for MNP risk related tools

Location: Online

Date: 21st April 2023

As part of CUSP's aim to investigate and discuss the applicability of existing risk assessment frameworks related to MNPs, CUSP project partners delivered three online workshops in the Spring of 2023 under the theme "Human Risk assessment of Micro- and Nanoplastics (MNPs)"². The third and final workshop was organized by PlasticsFatE partner BOKU and focused on data and information gaps.

²Workshop #1: Human Risk assessment of Micro- and Nanoplastics (MNPs) Regulatory insights and knowledge gaps. 7th February 2023 - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7625279>

This focused on regulatory insights and knowledge gaps and was organised by CUSP WG5 and PlasticHeal

Workshop #2: Human Risk Assessment of Micro- and Nanoplastics (MNPs) - Risk Assessment Frameworks

14th March 2023 - <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8042495> This focused on risk assessment frameworks and was organized by WG5 and Polyrisk

Programme and Speakers

CUSP
The European research cluster to understand the health impacts of micro- and nanoplastics

www.cusp-research.eu
hello@cusp-research.eu

CUSP thematic workshop series
Human Risk Assessment of MNPs
Register here: https://bit.ly/CUSP_WS3_Registration

Workshop #3/3
Practice-based analysis of data needs, availability, reuse and gaps for MNP-risk related tools
Friday 21st April 2023, 09:00-13:30 CEST

Preliminary Agenda

09:00 Welcome and summary of previous workshops from a data needs perspective
Rudolf Reuther and Bernd Giese, PlasticsFatE

I. Types of data needed for tools related to risk of MNP in CUSP and beyond

09:15 With input from:
POLYRISK: Andrea Haase
PlasticHeal: Steffen Foss Hansen
IMPTOX: Ivana Banic
PlasticsFatE: Dana Kühnel
PAPILLONS: Luca Nizetto

10:30 Coffee break

10:45 Preliminary summary on data needs
Christina Hipfinger, PlasticsFatE
Structured discussion about key requirements in terms of data

12:00 Coffee break

II. Data sources and data processing for risk related tools

12:10 Study quality assessment approach
Anita Jemec Kokalj, University of Ljubljana

12:25 Introduction to data sources /eNanoMapper, types and definitions of data
Nina Jeliakova, IDEAconsult Ltd

12:40 Conclusion and future steps

During the workshop we will invite you to answer four questions using mentimeter.
Go to www.menti.com
enter code 1834 6371
Or Use the QR code →

AURORA **IMP TOX** **plasticheal** **PlasticsFatE** **POLYRISK**

These projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreements AURORA n° 964827, IMPTOX n° 965173, PLASTICHEAL n° 965196, PLASTICFATE n° 965367, POLYRISK n° 964766.

Figure 8 Preliminary agenda for 3rd Workshop on Human Risk Assessment of MNPs

Participants

The workshops were open to participants from all CUSP projects. Each workshop was attended by over 100 participants.

Content and Proceedings:

The workshop aimed to address issues related to collection of input information required for characterisation of MNP risk by

1. Collecting, structuring data/format/quality requirements
2. Discuss options to solve the problems
3. Quality assessment for studies that produce the data
4. Review data sources including the character of the included data

In planning the content for the event, PlasticsFatE partners considered that an analysis of the risks associated with MNPs includes a number of aspects that should be factored in. In addition to information about the material itself, its applications and its life cycle, it is necessary to analyze the hazard and exposure to enable a risk characterization. Different methods can be

used for each part of the risk assessment process. For example, Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATAs) for hazard assessment or Material Flow Analysis (MFA) to provide a basis for calculating Predicted Environmental Concentrations (PECs) to estimate exposure.

A number of methods are being applied or newly developed in ongoing projects aimed at improving our understanding of the health effects of MNPs. Depending on which part of the risk assessment they belong to, they may require different kinds of input information. The type of data and their application to the methods provided a springboard for the workshop.

Contributions from the CUSP projects and the EU project PAPHILLONS on plastic in agricultural production detailed the overview of their approaches along the following questions:

1. What methods are you developing (or applying) for risk analysis/risk assessment?
2. What type of data do you need?
3. Are there any problems in collecting these data?
4. What sources do you use to obtain the data?

In a structured discussion, the participants tried to determine if the methods are compatible with the available data or if there are gaps or even problems with the format or quality of the data. A second part of the discussion was devoted to ideas on how to solve the problems identified. For example, sometimes the data exist somewhere but are hard to find, not harmonized, and not centralized in a common database, or are in larger data bodies such as eNanoMapper and/or IPCChem. In addition, the quality of the studies in which the data were generated also plays a role. These issues were addressed in two presentations in the second part of the workshop. In a final discussion the participants tried to concretize the further steps, taking into account the input from the second part of the workshop.

Impact

By examining specific methods such as IATAs and MFA, participants gained insights into the types of data required for different steps in the risk characterization process. Presentations and structured discussions allowed each project to share concrete examples of tools under development and their corresponding data needs, fostering mutual learning and potential collaboration.

The workshop also provided an opportunity to identify practical solutions, including improved data curation, the need for centralised and standardised data repositories, and the development of shared quality criteria for data sources. The outcome was a clearer understanding of the systemic barriers to effective data reuse and integration, as well as a roadmap for addressing these barriers within the CUSP framework.

Participants were equipped to apply the insights from this workshop in several ways:

- Tool development: Incorporate identified data requirements and quality standards into the design or refinement of risk assessment tools.
- Data strategy: Improve data collection strategies by aligning them with the data types and formats discussed during the workshop.

- Collaboration: Initiate data-sharing collaborations or joint efforts to build harmonized datasets based on shared challenges and needs, with a view to using eNanoMapper and/or IPCChem.
- Policy input: Use the workshop findings to support evidence-based recommendations for improving data infrastructure and governance for MNP risk assessment.
- Future research: Identify priority areas for research funding and project design, particularly concerning data availability, accessibility, and standardization.

The content, available via Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/8042627>), provides a reference for both current project work and long-term strategic planning related to human health risk assessment of micro- and nanoplastics.

2.5.2 Other Training

PlasticsFatE partners have also delivered the following training sessions:

Partner(s)	Description of training provided	Date
GAIKER	<p>Training session entitled "Assessment of environmental pollution and its impacts on human health" at the "Research in Environmental Contamination and Toxicology" event, held under the aegis of "Investigación en Contaminación y Toxicología Ambientales (INCyTA)", organised by Masters CTA and ECT+ and CTA PhD program (UPV/EHU) at the Marine Station of Plentzia, University of the Basque Country.</p> <p>Training was delivered to MSc and PhD students who were taught techniques to assess human health impacts of environmental pollution with special focus on in vitro methods. Alberto Katsumiti used as an example the approaches adopted in the PlasticsFatE project to evaluate the human health impacts of micro and nanoplastics on the gastrointestinal system. Participants were shown how to use different in vitro models for acute and subacute toxicity and how they can adapt the classical in vitro methods to expose human cells to micro and nanoplastics.</p>	10th June 2022
CSIC	Raman school organised by CHARISMA project with talks about microplastics characterisation from PlasticsFatE	18th -19th October 2022
UP	MSC (first year) course on "Emerging pollutions: nanoparticles and microplastics" with input from PlasticsFatE Training of MSc and PhD students	11th and 21st October 2023
IGB	Training on, "Determining horizontal gene transfer in presence of microplastics with focus on using Flow Cytometer Provided training to students and a Post-doc of Technical University of Liberec (TUL), Czech	12th-18th March 2023
UFZ & UL	COST Action PRIORITY workshop, invited oral presentation "Micro-and nano-plastics: presence and potential impact in the aquatic environment".	19th September 2023
IGB	Training on, "Determining horizontal gene transfer in presence of microplastics with focus on using Flow Cytometer Provided training to masters students of University of Potsdam	3rd-13th October 2023
UFZ	Lecturing at University of Leipzig, "Toxicological assessment of anthropogenic particles (nanomaterials + innovative materials, microplastics)", Postgraduate program in Toxicology and Environmental Protection	19th October 2023

UFZ & UL	Invited oral presentation OEA webinar "On the importance of study quality criteria for the hazard assessment of nanoplastics in aquatic organisms" https://www.oaepublish.com/webinars/wecn.233	24th November 2023
UFZ & UL	Oral presentation department seminar "On the importance of study quality criteria for the hazard assessment of nanoplastics in aquatic organisms"	29th November 2023

3. Summary

This deliverable set out to support ECRs and the wider scientific and regulatory communities by sharing emerging knowledge and tools developed within the PlasticsFatE project, particularly in relation to the detection, analysis and assessment of MNPs. Through a mix of physical and virtual training events, we aimed to make complex topics such as risk assessment, standardization, and hazard analysis more accessible and practically relevant.

While our ambition was to foster interdisciplinary exchange and build capacity across sectors, we recognize that translating scientific advances into widely usable training resources is an ongoing process. That said, feedback from participants suggests that the events were timely and valuable, and we were able to deliver all planned activities—plus several additional sessions—with strong engagement and contributions from across the consortium. In doing so, we made meaningful progress toward our goal of equipping the next generation of researchers with the knowledge and tools needed to address the challenges posed by MNPs.

4. Deviations from the Work plan

There have been no deviations from the work plan.

5. Performance of the partners

In addition to the valuable contributions of the partners listed as task contributors (UBT, UBA, STAMI, UFZ, UL, CNR-ISTEC, BOKU, ITENE, DECHEMA) the following partners have also provided essential input in the form of content and/or training delivery, as mentioned in section 2: UP, IGB, GAIKER, CSIC, UNITO, and ENAS

6. Conclusions

The Steering Board deems this deliverable to be fulfilled.

Abbreviations

A/C	Additives and adsorbed contaminants
CUSP	The European research cluster to understand the health impacts of micro- and nanoplastics (MNPs)
DSS	Decision Support System
ECRs	Early Career Researchers
IATA	Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment
MFA	Material Flow Analysis
MNPs	Micro and Nanoplastics
PEC	Predicted Environmental Concentration
PMCDs	Prospective Multi-Criteria Decision Support System for plastics
QA/QC	Quality Assurance/Quality Control